

Chitosan / *Trametes versicolor* laccase

nanostructures with modulated catalytic activity

Larisa-Maria Petrila¹, Timeea-Anastasia Ciobanu¹, Tudor Vasiliu¹,

Stergios Pispas^{1,2*}, Marcela Mihai^{1*}

¹Petru Poni Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry, 41A Grigore Ghica Voda Alley, 700487 Iasi, Romania

²Theoretical and Physical Chemistry Institute, National Hellenic Research Foundation, 48 Vassileos Constantinou Ave., 116 35 Athens, Greece

KEYWORDS: chitosan; laccase; nanoassemblies; indigo carmine; fluorescence spectroscopy.

ABSTRACT

Polymer/ enzyme nanoassemblies are a class of nanomaterials of increased interest for the medical, industrial or environmental fields. This study comprises a thorough scrutiny of the formation of nanoassemblies between *Trametes versicolor* laccase and a polysaccharide, chitosan, employing various experimental and theoretical methods. The binding mechanism was investigated through fluorescence quenching and molecular dynamics simulations, which identified key amino acids involved in the interaction. The modifications in the local environment of key fluorophores in the enzyme structure were detected using fluorescence spectroscopy, and the binding constant, number of binding sites, and quenching mechanism were assessed. At the same time, the nanoassemblies formation was confirmed by dynamic and electrophoretic light scattering, providing information

on their size, polydispersity, surface charge and stability. The catalytic activity of the formed nanoassemblies was assessed under various conditions, by ABTS oxidation and by the Indigo Carmine degradation tests. The obtained nanoassemblies exhibited enhanced stability in various experimental conditions (pH, temperature, storage) related to their catalytic activity.

INTRODUCTION

Laccases are enzymes involved in the phenolic or aromatic compounds oxidation by reducing molecular oxygen to water. They were identified in numerous organisms, including fungi (such as *Trametes*, *Myceliophthora* or *Laccaria*), bacteria (such as *Bacillus*, *Esterichia* or *Streptomyces*), but also insects (*Drosophila melanogaster*, *Nephotettix cincticeps*) and plants (*Oryza sativa*, *Nicotiana tabacum*, *Lolium perenne*)¹. White-rot fungi laccases are highly recognised catalysts for their large substrate specificity and their enhanced redox potential. The catalytic activity of laccases stems from their specific structure, which contains four copper atoms responsible for electron transfer activity and oxygen reduction¹⁻³. Fungal laccases have demonstrated promising utility in various technological fields, including the delignification of wood, bioremediation and degradation of various pollutants, biosensing, and catalysis⁴⁻⁶. While laccases are highly recognised for being efficient catalysts, their catalytic activity is strongly influenced by the environment, particularly by the possible interactions with other components in the media. This type of interaction may alter the enzyme's tertiary structure, influence its thermal stability and modulate its catalytic activity. Previous studies have indicated that the catalytic properties of laccases are related to their interaction with drugs, polymers, or metal nanoparticles⁷⁻⁹, and in some cases, significant unwanted changes to enzyme conformation (unfolding) might occur, leading to loss of activity. However, this is not universally the case, several studies demonstrate that specific compounds can have a beneficial effect on the enzyme structure and operational stability. Depending on the type

and strength of the interaction, the binding can have a stabilisation effect on the enzyme, leading to improved stability in various conditions or a modulation of the enzymatic activity. Of increased interest is the binding of polymers to proteins and especially enzymes, as the formation of a polymeric stabilising matrix potentially prevents the unfolding of the enzyme and protects it from harmful environmental factors¹⁰. This stabilisation effect is often attributed to favourable polymer-protein interactions that protect the enzyme's native conformation under various conditions. The interaction of proteins with charged polymers is possible due to the characteristic ampholyte structure of the proteins, which typically possess both positively and negatively chargeable functional groups^{11,12}. Depending on the environmental pH, the charging of specific residues is promoted, making possible the formation of electrostatic interactions with oppositely charged compounds¹³. Consequently, electrostatic interactions are fundamental in the binding and assembly of proteins and charged polymers. Nevertheless, weak interactions, including hydrophobic, hydrogen, and van der Waals ones, contribute significantly to the coupling of proteins and polymers, facilitating the formation of protein/polymer nanostructures, thus stabilising the so-formed nanoassemblies^{14,15}. This mechanism also explains the nanoassemblies formation between proteins and polyelectrolytes with similar surface charge, as thoughtfully discussed in the literature^{11,14,16}.

Among the studied polymers, chitosan (CHI) has been used in the study of protein/polymer interactions due to its natural origin and important properties, including biodegradability, biocompatibility, and antimicrobial activity^{17,18}. CHI is one of the most prevalent polysaccharides in nature, resulting from the partial deacetylation of chitin^{19,20}. It presents numerous properties that recommend it for various biomedical and industrial applications, with a particular interest in emerging applications such as tissue engineering, drug delivery, food preservation, environmental

protection, and enzyme immobilisation²¹⁻²³. More recently, the applicability of CHI has expanded significantly, driven by the occurrence of new chemical modification methods which led to the emergence of novel applications of interest, such as stimuli-responsive drug delivery, gene delivery, smart wound dressings or water purification technologies²⁴⁻²⁷. CHI has been remarked as a versatile polymer for the formation of protein/polyelectrolyte nanoassemblies, mainly reported with human serum albumin²⁸, horseradish peroxidase²⁹, catalase³⁰ or pepsin³¹. The binding of CHI to proteins is hypothesised to arise from a combination of electrostatic interactions between the -NH₃⁺ groups of CHI and protein amino acids negatively charged, but also from hydrophobic interactions and hydrogen bonds. Although the CHI and various proteins interaction was already studied, it is not yet fully established how CHI binding affects the conformational stability, catalytic efficiency, or substrate accessibility of enzymes under physiological and experimental conditions. The current study introduces a comprehensive investigation on the interaction of *Trametes versicolor* laccase (LAC) and CHI, employing various experimental and theoretical methods. The binding mechanism was investigated through fluorescence quenching experiments and molecular dynamics simulations, which identified key amino acids involved in the interaction. Moreover, the modifications in the local environment of key fluorophores in the enzyme structure were detected using fluorescence spectroscopy, and the binding constant (K_a), number of binding sites (n), and quenching mechanism were determined. Additionally, enzyme catalytic activity experiments were utilised to assess the CHI effect on catalytic activity and substrate affinity and the stability of the LAC/CHI complexes in various experimental conditions. In an attempt to emphasise potential applications of the LAC/CHI complexes, the enzymatic degradation of a model dye - Indigo Carmine (IC) - was studied.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials

The chemicals used in this study were acquired as follows: CHI with $M_w = 162$ Kg/mol and 88.2% deacetylation degree (according to the supplier), from Shandong AK Biotech Co., Ltd. (Jinan, China); *T. versicolor* laccase with an activity ≥ 0.5 U/mg (according to the producer) and 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) from Sigma Aldrich (Germany); IC from VWR Chemicals; syringaldehyde (SG) from Alfa Aesar. All the compounds were utilised without further purification.

LAC/CHI nanoassemblies preparation

A stock solution of LAC (0.5 mg/mL in acetate buffer, pH = 4.5, 0.1 M) and a stock solution of CHI (1 mg/mL in acetate buffer, pH = 4.5, 0.1 M) were prepared and left to equilibrate overnight at 4 °C and then passed through a syringe filter of 0.45 μm to remove any impurity or undissolved residues. The pH and ionic strength of the buffer solution were selected according to previous studies³² to ensure a satisfactory enzymatic activity of *T. versicolor* LAC, as well as a good ionisation of the functional groups on both LAC and CHI as to ensure the formation of electrostatic interactions. The electrostatic nanoassemblies were prepared under gentle stirring at room temperature by mixing a constant volume of LAC solution (4 mL) with different volumes of the CHI solution (0.5 – 4 mL) and a corresponding volume of acetate buffer up to 10 mL final volume. The prepared nanoassemblies were kept overnight at 4 °C to equilibrate before characterisation. In this manner, the electrostatic complexes at various mass ratios were prepared, their code used in this study being LAC/CHI_r, where r is the mass ratio between components in the mixture.

Characterisation methods

By fluorescence spectroscopy, the binding of CHI to LAC and the potential alterations in the enzyme tertiary structure during interaction with the polymer were monitored. For this, stock solutions of LAC (3.57×10^{-5} M) and CHI (6.17×10^{-6} M) were prepared in acetate buffer solution and left overnight to equilibrate, followed by filtering as described above. The fluorescence spectra of LAC and LAC/CHI mixtures at increasing CHI contents were registered in 10 mm quartz cuvettes, by exciting the samples at 280 nm with room temperature scanning at 300-450 nm, using the FLS5 photoluminescence spectrometer (Edinburgh Instruments, Livingston, UK). Small volumes of the polymer solution were used to make sure that the dilution effect is negligible. The maximum intensity was determined at the emission wavelength 325 nm, and the quenching parameters were calculated from the corresponding values, applying the Stern-Volmer equation. Additionally, the thermodynamic parameters of CHI/LAC binding were calculated by performing fluorescence spectroscopy studies at various temperatures (298 – 308 K), following the procedure described above, and applying the Van't Hoff plot.

To investigate the molecular interactions responsible for the formation of the nanoassemblies between LAC and CHI and to test if CHI has any effect on the thermal stability of the enzyme, four molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were conducted, two with LAC alone, solvated in water at 298 K and 333 K, and two with LAC in the presence CHI, also performed at 298 K and 333 K. The simulations were realised using the AMBER force field on both the enzyme and polymer fragments, along with the water model TIP3P. The LAC structural coordinates were collected from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (PDB ID: 1KYA)³³. All simulations were run using GROMACS³⁴ version 2024.2 at 298K/333K with V-rescale temperature coupling ($\tau = 0.5$ ps). Pressure was upheld with the Parrinello–Rahman barostat with isotropic coupling, a 2.0 ps time constant, and 4.5×10^{-5} bar⁻¹ compressibility. The systems were simulated for a total of 1 μ s with

a 2 fs integration time step. After energy minimisation (50,000 steps steepest descent + 50,000 steps conjugate gradient), each system underwent a three-stage equilibration: (i) 500 ps NVT heating from 0 K to the target temperature with positional restraints on all heavy atoms ($1000 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ nm}^{-2}$); (ii) 1 ns NPT at the target temperature/1 bar with restraints linearly reduced to $0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ nm}^{-2}$; (iii) 10 ns unrestrained NPT to allow volume and density stabilisation.

The CHI binding effect on the self-assembly of LAC was evaluated based on dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements, using a Litesizer 500 equipment with a single-frequency laser diode of 40 mW running at 658 nm (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria), the measurements being performed at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a 90° angle. The software Kalliope (version 3.2.4) was used to analyse the collected data. The zeta potential measurements were performed with the same equipment, at a 175° scattering angle and $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The nanoassemblies samples prepared in acetate buffer, as described above, were used without further dilution.

Among the prepared LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies, two samples (LAC/CHI₂ and LAC/CHI_{0.5}) were selected for further characterisation. Their selection aimed to target samples prepared with lower and higher CHI contents for comparative purposes, additionally taking into consideration the results of preliminary characterisation by DLS and ELS. The ionic strength impact on the selected LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies was assessed by titrating the samples with increasing amounts of 1 M NaCl. After 10 minutes of equilibration, DLS measurements were performed.

The LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies' morphology and size were evaluated employing the Verios G4 UC (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) scanning electron microscope operated in high-vacuum mode, at 20 kV, using the STEM 3+ detector. The analyses were performed by depositing small aliquots of selected LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies on copper grids of 300 mesh covered with a carbon film, left to dry for a week before analysis.

Catalytic activity

The LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies' catalytic activity was evaluated based on ABTS oxidation. Thus, the ABTS solution (pH = 4.5, 0.1 M) was brought in contact with a given volume of LAC solution or LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies and incubated at 25 °C. The increase in absorbance at $\lambda = 420$ nm was registered using the Spekol 1300 Plus UV-VIS Spectrophotometer (Analytic Jena, Germany), and the LAC enzymatic activity was estimated from the absorbance variation; one unit of activity represents the enzyme amount necessary to oxidise in one minute one μmol of ABTS. The experiments were triplicated, and the average values with the standard deviation are graphically represented.

Based on the results of the catalytic activity tests, the two selected samples, namely (LAC/CHI_{0.5} and LAC/CHI₂), were considered more representative for emphasising the role of CHI amount in the catalytic properties of the obtained nanoassemblies and were selected for further characterisation. The catalytic activity of selected nanoassemblies and the LAC solution after being kept at 4 °C for 50 days was estimated by means of enzymatic activity determination using ABTS as substrate, in the conditions stated above.

To assess the pH-dependent activity of LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies, the catalytic activity of selected samples was evaluated using ABTS solutions prepared at various pH values, under the assay conditions already presented.

The stability of LAC after its interaction with CHI was evaluated by incubating selected LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies and the initial LAC solution (used as a control) at various temperatures for 15 minutes, in agreement with previous studies³⁵. The residual catalytic activity after incubation was assessed following the above-presented methodology, after cooling the samples at

room temperature. For all the methods concerning enzymatic activity, three sets of experiments were done, presenting the average value corrected with the standard deviation.

The kinetic parameters of LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies were experimentally determined by measuring the initial reaction velocities at increasing ABTS concentrations (0.1 – 1 mM, pH = 4.5). The Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) and maximum reaction rate (V_{max}) were determined from the Lineweaver-Burk plot. The turnover number, k_{cat} , was estimated by the equation (1).

$$k_{cat} = V_{max}/[E] \quad (1)$$

where [E] is the initial LAC concentration.

The effect of CHI interaction on the LAC enzymatic activity was also assessed by testing the degradation of IC catalysed by LAC and selected LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies. Aqueous solutions of IC of various concentrations (25-75 mg/L) were added to a volume of LAC solution or selected LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies, using SG as a redox mediator. The dye degradation was assessed by registering the absorbance at 610 nm with the spectrophotometer Spekol 1300 Plus UV-VIS (Analytic Jena, Germany).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fluorescence quenching

The interaction between LAC and CHI was investigated using fluorescence spectroscopy, taking advantage of the technique's high sensitivity, simplicity, and well-established theoretical foundation. Owing to the aromatic amino acids, such as tryptophan, phenylalanine and tyrosine, LAC exhibits intrinsic fluorescence. The role of tryptophan in the fluorescence emission of LAC is significant since LAC presents seven tryptophan residues³⁶. The interaction between LAC and CHI could potentially lead to modifications of the tryptophan residues, indicating alterations in the local microenvironment around fluorophores and providing evidence of molecular binding³⁶⁻³⁸.

The effect of CHI presence on the LAC fluorescence is closely connected to the accessibility of the tryptophan residues, with the residues closer to the surface being more prone to interact, while the tryptophan residues less exposed to the surface being less prone to interact with CHI. The attenuation in fluorescence intensity upon binding of a compound to a molecule exhibiting fluorescence is known as quenching and results from different molecular interactions, which often include rearrangements, collisional quenching, and others³⁹. The two primary quenching mechanisms are: (a) static, involving a complex in the ground-state, non-fluorescent, formed by the fluorophore and the quencher, and (b) dynamic, occurring through collisional interactions in the excited state³⁹. Understanding the fluorescence quenching mechanism is essential in elucidating the molecular interaction mechanism in the studied system.

For a more thorough understanding of the nature of the binding between LAC and CHI, the LAC fluorescence spectra were recorded at various concentrations of CHI, at temperatures 298, 303, and 308 K. Upon increasing the CHI concentration in the mixture, the fluorescence intensity of LAC decreased, as evidenced in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Fluorescence spectra of LAC before (red line) and after titration (dashed lines) with CHI, at 298 K (a), 303 K (b), 308 K (c), and relative fluorescence intensity upon CHI titration (d). The arrow on each figure signifies the decrease in the fluorescence intensity of LAC with the increase in the volume of CHI added from 0 to 1.23 μM .

The studies conducted at the three temperatures indicate an evident quenching, confirming the binding of CHI to LAC (**Figure 1**). The decrease in fluorescence intensity upon CHI binding suggests modifications in the local microenvironment around the tryptophan residues, which decrease the fluorophores' accessibility. In what concerns the overall aspect of the fluorescence spectra get together in Figure 1, up to an added volume of CHI of 500 μL (corresponding to a CHI concentration of 1.23 μM), there is no evident change in the characteristics of the spectra, the emission maxima being preserved, a fact that serves as further proof that the binding of CHI does not lead to enzyme denaturation or important conformational changes. A similar effect is observed when temperature increases, with an attenuation of the fluorescence intensity, but a conservation of the position of the maximum emission peak.

Binding parameters upon interaction between CHI and LAC

Even if the fluorescence spectra characteristics offer valuable information about the effect of CHI binding on the structural integrity of the enzyme, it is not sufficient to explain the interaction in the LAC/CHI system. Additional information about the mechanism of quenching is usually obtained based on the binding constant values. The equation Stern–Volmer (eq. 2) and its double logarithmic form (eq. 3) were employed to understand the quenching mechanism and the interaction between LAC and CHI:

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{SV}[Q] = 1 + k_q \tau_0 [Q] \quad (2)$$

$$\log \frac{F_0 - F}{F} = \log K_a + n \log [Q] \quad (3)$$

where F_0 and F - intensities of the fluorescence of the free LAC and LAC/CHI mixtures, K_{SV} - the quenching constant of Stern–Volmer, k_q - bimolecular quenching constant, Q - CHI molar concentration, τ_0 - average fluorescence lifetime in the excited state of the protein when no quencher is present (τ_0 for tryptophan is $\sim 10^{-8}$ seconds)^{8,40}, K_a - apparent binding constant, n - binding sites number. The K_{SV} was determined by representing the $F_0/F = f(Q)$, whereas K_a and n were determined from the double logarithmic Stern-Volmer plot, presented in **Figure S1 (Supplementary information)**, which demonstrate the good linearity between F_0/F in relation to the CHI concentration within the tested limits, suggesting that the system undergoes quenching either by static or dynamic mechanisms. To determine the K_{SV} , a linear regression model was applied to fit the obtained results. The K_{SV} and k_q values at each temperature are summarized in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Stern-Volmer quenching constant (K_{sv}), bimolecular quenching constant (k_q), apparent binding constant (K_a), and number of binding sites (n) values for LAC interactions with CHI, at different temperatures. R^2 - correlation coefficient.

Temperature (K)	$K_{SV} (M^{-1})$	$k_q (M^{-1} s^{-1})$	R^2	$K_a (M^{-1})$	n	R^2
298	$1.56 \cdot 10^5$	$1.56 \cdot 10^{13}$	0.991	$6.30 \cdot 10^4$	0.93	0.987
303	$1.73 \cdot 10^5$	$1.73 \cdot 10^{13}$	0.985	$6.45 \cdot 10^3$	0.76	0.989
308	$1.90 \cdot 10^5$	$1.90 \cdot 10^{13}$	0.980	$4.78 \cdot 10^3$	0.73	0.990

As presented in Table 1, K_{SV} increases slightly with temperature, suggesting a more efficient quenching, as also reported for the interaction of CHI with bovine serum albumin²⁸ and the interaction of CHI-graphene oxide nanocomposites with β -galactosidase⁴¹. The increase in K_{SV} can be associated with an enhancement in molecular motion due to temperature, which favours the interaction between the molecules in the system but does not necessarily imply stronger binding. The increased quenching observed with increasing temperature could also be the result of the thermally induced unfolding of the enzyme, leading to the uncovering of tryptophan residues, enhancing the chances of interaction with the quencher. The mechanism of quenching can be assumed based on the value of the k_q constant, taking into consideration that for dynamic quenching processes, the maximum k_q value for various quenchers is typically around $2 \cdot 10^{10} (M^{-1} s^{-1})$ ^{39,42}. The calculated k_q values for the LAC/CHI_r systems (**Table 1**) are higher than $1.5 \cdot 10^{13} M^{-1} s^{-1}$, leading to the assumption that the observed quenching mechanism is static³⁹. A comparable effect was found for the quenching of various proteins in the presence of CHI or CHI-derivatives, including sodium caseinate⁴², casein⁴³, ovalbumin⁴⁴, β -lactoglobulin⁴⁵, bovine^{28,46} or human serum albumins²⁸. For example, Bekale et al.²⁸ observed a similar effect upon the binding of CHI to bovine serum albumin, emphasising that the molecular weight of CHI plays an important role in the interaction with the protein. Similarly, Agudelo et al.⁴⁵ reported the fact that the binding of CHI to β -lactoglobulin occurs through a static quenching mechanism.

The temperature impact on the interaction of LAC and CHI can be evaluated based on the constant K_a and the number of sites of binding, estimated by the double logarithmic Stern-Volmer plot (**Figure S1**). As observed from the values in **Table 1**, at ambient temperature, there is about one site for CHI binding. The constant K_a decreases with temperature, suggesting that the binding is less favourable at increasing temperatures, and the stability of the formed ground state complex decreases with increasing temperatures, as also observed for other systems involving proteins⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. Such a behaviour is expected since temperature increases the molecular motion, favouring the collision between molecules, but not their binding, which is an expected effect in the context of weak interactions, which are generally distorted upon an increase in temperature. Additionally, temperature influences the conformation of biological molecules, increasing or decreasing the accessibility of the binding sites or leading to partial denaturation or unfolding, which might alter previously accessible binding sites.

Thermodynamic parameters

Valuable information about the type of interactions that occur between LAC and CHI can be obtained from the changes in enthalpy (ΔH), entropy (ΔS), and Gibbs free energy (ΔG) values. When the variation in enthalpy in the studied system is not significant, ΔH and ΔS are usually determined by means of Van't Hoff equation (eq. 4):

$$\ln K_a = - \frac{\Delta H}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (4)$$

where K_a - binding constant at each investigated temperature, R - ideal gas constant ($R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and T - temperature (K). Then, the ΔH and ΔS values were determined from the slope and intercept of the linear representation, respectively, whereas changes in the Gibbs free energy can be calculated with the equation (5):

$$\Delta G = - RT \ln K_a \quad (5)$$

The nature of the interactions between CHI and LAC can be inferred from the determined thermodynamic parameters, considering that $\Delta G < 0$ denote spontaneous binding. When $\Delta H > 0$ and $\Delta S > 0$, mainly hydrophobic interactions occur; when $\Delta H < 0$ and $\Delta S > 0$, the binding is mainly due to electrostatic interactions, while when $\Delta H < 0$ and $\Delta S < 0$, the binding occurs due to van der Waals and hydrogen bonding^{50,51}.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters for LAC and CHI binding

Temperature (K)	ΔH (KJ/mol)	ΔS (KJ/mol · K)	ΔG (KJ/mol)
298	-197.6	-0.57	-27.38
303			-22.10
308			-21.69

Based on values presented in **Table 2**, it can be observed that both ΔH and ΔS are < 0 , indicating that the binding of CHI and LAC occurs mostly based on the hydrogen bonds and van der Waals interactions. The ΔG negative value implies a spontaneous process⁵². The obtained binding and thermodynamic parameters provide strong evidence of the LAC/CHI interaction, with weak interactions favouring the binding process. These molecular interactions depend on concentration, pH, temperature and ionic strength and could imply the formation of enzyme-based nanoassemblies upon CHI binding.

Molecular dynamics simulations

MD simulations were conducted aiming at two aspects: 1) to determine the residues of the enzyme that interact the most with CHI, and 2) to check if CHI exhibits any role in the thermal stability of LAC. To this end, four systems were designed, two containing just the LAC in water and two containing both LAC and CHI. Simulations were run at 298 K (≈ 25 °C) to mimic ambient

conditions and at 333 K (≈ 60 °C) to probe the enzyme close to its experimental melting point ($T_m \approx 330$ – 338 K for fungal laccases⁵³). Operating just below T_m accelerates the onset of partially unfolded states within the 1 μ s simulation window, enabling qualitative assessment of thermal destabilisation and any protective effect conferred by CHI. The initial and final conformations resulting from the MD simulations at 298K are presented in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Initial and final conformations of a) LAC (cartoon representation) and b) LAC in the presence of CHI (quick-surface representation). Each structural region of the enzyme is coloured as follows: alpha-helix in purple, beta-sheets in yellow, and random coils in teal and white. CHI chains are represented as licorice, and the atoms are coloured as follows: carbon in teal, nitrogen in blue, oxygen in red, and hydrogen in white.

As evidenced in **Figure 2a**, the structure of the enzyme suffers minimal changes over the entire simulation. More so, **Figure 2b** shows that the CHI chains adhere just to the surface of the enzyme,

without any polymer getting inside the LAC structure. To better quantify the changes in the LAC structure and how the variations in temperature and the presence of the CHI influence these changes, a Root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) analysis was performed, presented in **Figure 3**. Unaveraged RMSD data are presented for comparison in **Figure S2, Supporting information**.

Figure 3. Analysis of root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) of LAC over the full simulation trajectory, averaged over 1000 frames to improve clarity.

As evidenced in **Figure 3**, the RMSD of the LAC simulation increases with the increase in temperature (from 1.5 to about 4 Å), which is to be expected due to thermal denaturation of the enzyme. In what concerns the CHI presence, it can be observed that the polysaccharide has a stabilising effect on the enzyme, as the RMSD values in the simulations where CHI is present are lower than in the simulations without CHI, irrespective of the simulated temperature, confirming its protective effect. The convergence of the RMSD in the simulations can be observed by the plateauing of the values in the last 250ns (10,000 frames).

Also, the MD simulations were used to emphasise which residues of the protein are interacting with the CHI functional groups (acetylate for hydrophobic interaction, -OH for hydrogen bonds, -NH⁺₃ for electrostatic interactions), the number of contacts that take place between CHI and each type of amino acid present in the LAC, summed up over the entire course of the simulation being presented in **Table S1, Supporting information**. The analysis of the contacts presented in **Table S1** shows two main trends: 1) the temperature increase induces the formation of more contacts between LAC and CHI and 2) CHI comes in contact the most with THR, PRO, ALA, SER, LEU amino acids (in this order) at 298K and with ALA, THR, ASP, PRO and ASN (in this order) at 333K. This behaviour supports the formation of electrostatic and hydrogen interactions between LAC and CHI, and also of some hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions among the acetylated residues of the polymers and amino acids like PRO and ALA, confirming the interaction mechanism determined from the quenching studies.

Although the Amber ff14SB/GLYCAM06 force-field combination with the TIP3P water model reproduces backbone flexibility and CHI-protein contacts reasonably well, it neglects explicit electronic polarisation and may under-estimate long-range electrostatics. In addition, the 1 μ s trajectories (single replica per condition) sample only early unfolding events; millisecond-scale cooperative denaturation and rare binding modes may therefore be missed. Our MD results should thus be viewed as qualitative trends complementary to the experimental data, not as exhaustive thermodynamic predictions.

Formation of LAC/CHI_n nanoassemblies

As observed from the fluorescence quenching experiments and the MD simulations, the interaction of LAC with CHI leads to nanoassemblies in solution, resulting from the formation of weak interactions, such as electrostatic or hydrophobic ones. The formation of nanoassemblies

between CHI and LAC was studied at increasing CHI concentrations (**Table 3**) by means of DLS measurements, following the variation in the average size, scattered light intensity, and polydispersity of the formed nanoassemblies (**Figure S3, Supporting information**).

Table 3. Scattered light intensity, average diameter and polydispersity indexes of LAC/CHI_r nanostructures, as a function of mass ratio (r) between components.

r	Scattered intensity (kHz)	Average diameter (nm)	Polydispersity index
2	72.3	336±7	0.37±0.02
1	64.5	249±5	0.32±0.01
0.5	27.0	241±2	0.29±0.02
0.25	21.6	205±11	0.32±0.02

The LAC/CHI interaction is also sustained by the DLS measurements, where the increase in scattered intensity with CHI concentration indicates the progressive formation of nanostructured assemblies between the two components⁵⁴. Accordingly, the size of the obtained nanoassemblies increases with the CHI concentration. This effect can be explained by the binding mechanism of CHI, with more CHI chains binding to the enzyme or covering its surface more extensively, as also observed from the MD simulations (**Figure 2**). This observation is further supported by the corresponding increase in the average hydrodynamic diameters, as recorded in **Table 3**. The relatively low polydispersity index values across all samples point to the formation of nanostructures with relatively uniform size distributions, even if the formed nanostructures might have different sizes (as suggested by the DLS profiles in **Figure S3, Supporting information**), but a relatively homogeneous size range is expected.

Zeta potential measurements provide insights into the overall charge of the formed nanoassemblies. LAC itself has a negative zeta potential (-5 mV) at pH = 4.5. Also, the performed zeta potential measurements (**Figure 4**) reveal that all the formed nanoassemblies are positively charged. This observation supports the hypothesis that CHI chains interact with the amino acids at the enzyme surface, likely through electrostatic attractions and hydrogen bonding, partially covering the enzyme and leaving the positive functional groups of CHI exposed at the surface. A similar variation in zeta potential was observed by Li and co-workers, who studied the formation of interpolyelectrolyte complexes between CHI and α -lactoglobulin extracted from whey⁵⁵, and by Bourouis and co-workers, which studied the complexation of soy proteins with CHI⁵⁶, concluding that upon interaction, the protein is surrounded by CHI chains, with the positive charge of CHI dictating the overall charge of the new nanostructures. This phenomenon is mainly expected for proteins such as LAC, which adopt a globular conformation, favouring the deposition of a polymeric shell due to surface interactions.

Figure 4. Zeta potential values of initial CHI and LAC solutions and the LAC nanostructures formed upon interaction with various concentrations of CHI.

Additionally, the zeta potential values measured for the formed nanostructures are lower than the zeta potential of the initial CHI solution, demonstrating that an important role in the LAC/CHI binding is played by the process of partial neutralization of the opposite charges on the CHI and LAC chains, and the formation of electrostatic interactions between the two macromolecules.

Storage stability

The stability of the formed nanoassemblies is a critical factor in assessing their potential use in various fields, including biomedical, environmental or catalytic applications. To evaluate the long-term stability of the samples, selected nanoassemblies were kept at 4 °C for 50 days. The stability of the samples was assessed based on DLS and zeta potential measurements. Generally, upon storage, nanostructures can undergo physicochemical changes such as aggregation or surface modifications, which can potentially be detected by DLS or ELS measurements. As evidenced in **Table S2, Supporting information**, the nanoassemblies exhibit insignificant variation in the average diameters and a small decrease in the polydispersity indexes. Moreover, no sign of macroscopic aggregation or sedimentation was observed, further confirming the stability of the formed nanoassemblies. The zeta potential values decrease slightly upon storage, suggesting minimal changes in the surface properties of the analysed samples. This could be ascribed to the surface sorption of ions from the environment by the nanoassemblies. However, the changes recorded in the average diameter and zeta potential of the samples are minor, suggesting that the nanoassemblies are rather stable upon storage for 50 days.

The formation and storage stability of the obtained LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies were additionally confirmed from the registered STEM micrographs (**Figure 5**). As evidenced in the micrographs in Figure 5, the nanoassemblies appear nearly spherical and moderately uniform in size and shape, as expected for self-assembled protein-based nanostructures, a phenomenon also observed in other

systems comprising proteins and polymers^{57,58}. The size distribution of the observed nanoassemblies evidences the presence of structures of various sizes, correlating with the two-sized population observed in DLS profiles in **Figure S3**. Moreover, the STEM micrographs evidence a structure with a denser core and a lighter surrounding shell, suggesting that CHI forms a coating around LAC aggregates, resulting in core-shell nanostructures, supporting the MD simulation in **Figure 2b**.

Figure 5. STEM micrographs of the LAC/CHI₂ nanoassemblies (a) before and (b) after 50 days of storage, scale bar 300 nm and magnification x100 k. Insets are corresponding micrographs with scale bar 500 nm and magnification x50 k.

Additionally, the STEM micrographs registered after 50 days of storage evidence a good stability, the samples presenting similar shapes and the apparent size distribution being preserved over time. Even if a small degree of aggregation is observed, the samples seem rather stable upon storage. However, it should be noted that the interpretation of STEM micrographs may be affected by inherent resolution limitations and sample-related artefacts due to the drying process or the degradation of the sample upon electron beam exposure.

Ionic strength influence on the stability of the formed nanoassemblies

As previously reported, ionic strength has a strong impact on the stability of the nanoassemblies formed by weak interactions⁵⁹. The increasing ionic strength can potentially disrupt weak interactions by screening charged functional groups or increasing the electrostatic repulsions between molecules in solution, decreasing their chances of interaction¹⁴. The ionic strength impact on the LAC and CHI interactions was studied in the presence of increasing amounts of 1 M NaCl, by analysing the average size and the scattered intensity of the nanoassemblies upon NaCl titration (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Scattered intensity (a) and average diameters (b) of LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies prepared at various CHI concentrations and different ionic strengths.

As presented in **Figure 6a**, the scattered intensity of the selected samples does not exhibit an important variation with increasing ionic strength. While generally the addition of salt can distort nanoassemblies formed by weak interactions due to the shielding of attractive electrostatic interactions and the disruption of weak bonds, the investigated system exhibits good stability to salt addition in the investigated concentration range. Such a behaviour might suggest that the formed complexes are rather tightly packed and stable upon variation in the surrounding media conditions. This effect may also be due, to some extent, to the polysaccharide used, which contains

lactate and phosphate counterions introduced during the synthesis step to increase its solubility in water⁶⁰. Thus, the presence of these counterions confers a superior stability of the polysaccharide to ionic strength variations, which is also preserved in the case of LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies. As a result, titration of the nanoassemblies with NaCl does not induce significant changes, as the small chlorine ions cannot displace the massive counterions on the polysaccharide backbone due to the steric effects that may partially compensate for the screening of electrostatic interactions in saline environments. The stability of the formed nanoassemblies to variation of the ionic strength is also confirmed by the fact that the suspensions did not show phase separation or increased turbidity upon addition of NaCl. Also, the sizes of the LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies (**Figure 6b**) are rather stable upon NaCl titration, suggesting no important interaction between the nanoassemblies and the salt, assuming a rather lower impact of electrostatic interactions in the creation of the nanoassemblies. Besides electrostatic interactions, hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions contribute to the formation of stable nanoassemblies. Moreover, the presence of specific polymer-associated counterions and potential steric hindrances may also play a role in the stabilisation of the nanoassemblies. These interactions can lead to increased stability of the formed nanoassemblies, which limits aggregation even at increased ionic strength. Although the average hydrodynamic diameter of the LAC/CHI_r structures remained almost unchanged upon ionic strength increase, some rearrangements and compaction of the formed complexes might occur.

Effect of CHI interaction on the LAC catalytic activity

The evaluation of the enzymatic activity of nanoassemblies formed by the interaction of LAC with CHI is of increasing importance in evidencing the influence of the polysaccharide on the enzymatic activity of LAC. ABTS is a chromogenic substrate for LAC that generates a green reaction product upon enzymatic oxidation. The enzymatic activity of selected LAC/CHI_r

nanoassemblies was studied by following the oxidation of ABTS to ABTS⁺ in optimised conditions³² and was compared with the activity of the initial LAC solution, as presented in **Figure 7a**. Thus, at lower concentrations of CHI (LAC/CHI_{0.5}), the enzymatic activity of LAC is not strongly affected by the formation of nanoassemblies. However, an increase in the catalytic activity of less than 3% for the mentioned nanoassemblies and less than 10% for nanoassemblies LAC/CHI₂, respectively, is observed, which may suggest that CHI stabilises the enzyme structure, improving the accessibility of the enzyme's active center. The increase in catalytic activity in the case of LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies may also be ascribed to changes produced by the complexation with CHI, which can induce changes in the enzyme's microenvironment, reducing electrostatic repulsions between the enzyme and the substrate, or enhancing secondary interactions that allow the substrate-enzyme interaction. A similar effect on the enzymatic activity upon interaction with polymers was observed by Boeris and collaborators, who studied the interaction of chymotrypsin with various polymers, including polyvinyl sulfonate (PVS), polyacrylic acid (PAA), and polyethylene oxide (PEO)⁶¹. The authors observed that while PAA does not strongly influence the catalytic activity of the enzyme, the interaction with PVS or PEO leads to ~ 60% and ~ 30% boost in the activity of chymotrypsin, respectively. A significant enhancement in the activity of horseradish peroxidase upon complexation with CHI was reported by Veselova and collaborators, who observed that the enzymatic activity of the formed complexes depended strongly on the CHI molar mass and the amount of polysaccharide used for the complex formation²⁹.

Figure 7. LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies' catalytic activity and storage stability (a), as well as the catalytic activity vs pH (b) and temperature (c) variations.

The stabilisation effect of CHI is also evidenced upon the long-term storage of the samples, as presented in **Figure 7a** for selected samples. Thus, the LAC/CHI_r nanostructures preserve a better catalytic activity after 50 days of storage at 4 °C, as compared to the free LAC, which loses about 65% of its activity. Additionally, it can be observed that the protective role of the CHI is dependent on the amount of used polysaccharide, with a better preservation of the catalytic activity for the LAC/CHI₂ nanoassemblies.

Another important aspect related to the catalytic activity of enzymes is their stability under different experimental conditions. In this regard, the pH influence on the LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies' enzymatic activity was studied using ABTS solutions prepared at different pH values. As **Figure 7b** shows, the highest enzymatic activity is observed at pH = 3.5 for both free LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies, a value that ensures the best conditions for the catalytic reaction, as also reported elsewhere³². Further pH increases determine a sharp reduction in the catalytic activity, a trend that is maintained for both free enzyme and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies. It is noteworthy to mention that at higher pH values, the catalytic activity is slightly higher for the LAC/CHI nanoassemblies than for the enzyme solution analysed under similar conditions, suggesting that while the optimal pH of the formed nanoassemblies is the same as for the free LAC (pH = 3.5), the nanoassemblies exhibit a better catalytic activity even at pH variations which is most likely the result of the CHI's protective role on the enzyme, probably due to an organic barrier formed at the surface of the enzyme which partially protects the enzyme from the negative impact of variations in environmental conditions. This behaviour is especially accentuated in the case of the LAC/CHI₂ nanoassemblies, which present higher catalytic activities at all the tested pH values, suggesting that the protective role of CHI is dependent on the amount of polymer used in the preparation of the nanoassemblies.

A comparable effect is observed when analysing the thermal stability of the LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies after incubation at various temperatures (**Figure 7c**). Thus, both free LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies tend to lose catalytic activity when incubated at higher temperatures, but in the case of the LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies, the catalytic activity observed after incubation is higher, suggesting a better preservation of the structural integrity of the enzyme compared to the free LAC in solution, as also confirmed by the MD simulations performed (**Figure 3**). In both pH

and temperature variations, it can be observed that the samples obtained after the interaction of LAC with higher CHI concentrations (sample LAC/CHI₂) preserve better their characteristics as compared to the samples with less CHI (sample LAC/CHI_{0.5}), supporting the claim that the CHI involved in the formation of the nanoassemblies has a protective role for LAC. Such behaviour is commonly reported in enzymes coated with polymers or enzymes embedded in polymer-based nanoassemblies, highlighting the potential advantages of this method in preserving, under various experimental conditions, the catalytic performance of enzymes^{62,63}. Overall, it could be observed that the formed LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies displayed an enhanced stability to both pH and temperature compared with the enzyme in solution, indicating that the CHI contributes to the preservation of the structural integrity of the enzyme.

The CHI complexation influence on the enzymatic activity of LAC was also assessed by calculating the corresponding K_m and V_{max} values for the free enzyme and selected nanoassemblies, respectively. K_m is the substrate concentration at which the enzyme operates at half the maximum conversion rate, effectively reflecting the affinity between the enzyme and substrate, while V_{max} refers to the maximum substrate conversion rate when the enzyme is fully saturated with substrate. Variations in K_m and V_{max} upon enzyme immobilisation, complexation or conjugation to polymers reflect the efficiency of the biocatalyst, highlighting potential inhibitions or changes in the enzyme structure or conformation. **Figure 8a** presents the variation of enzymatic activity in relation to the substrate concentration, and **Figure 8b** presents the Lineweaver-Burk plots for the free and complexed LAC, while the kinetic parameters for free and complexed LAC are presented in **Table 4**.

Figure 8. (a) Effect of substrate concentration on the catalytic activity of free and complexed LAC and (b) Lineweaver-Burk double-reciprocal plots for the free and complexed LAC.

As observed from **Figure 8a**, there is no important variation in the catalytic performance of the LAC/CHI_{0.5} compared with the free LAC, as also demonstrated by the similar values of K_m and V_{max} (**Table 4**). This behaviour suggests that the complexation of LAC with low concentrations of CHI ($r = 0.5$) preserves the enzyme conformation and maintains the accessibility to its catalytic center. On the other hand, the complexation of LAC with a higher concentration of CHI ($r = 2$) leads to a small increase in the K_m and V_{max} values, which might suggest an alteration of substrate binding, mainly in the case of the LAC/CHI₂ nanoassemblies. Such a behaviour can be the result of a decrease in the accessibility of the catalytic center due to CHI binding, which potentially hinders the catalytic site, reduces the enzyme flexibility or changes the polarity of the microenvironment of the enzyme. While the higher value of K_m might imply a slightly lower affinity of the nanoassemblies towards the substrate due to steric constraints in the interaction of the substrate with the catalytic site, the increasing value of k_{cat} suggests a better catalytic efficiency in the oxidation of ABTS, confirming the stabilisation effect of CHI binding on the enzyme

conformation, as also observed in the pH and temperature stability tests. This increase in the k_{cat} can be correlated with possible conformational changes that occur upon CHI binding, and which might stabilise the catalytic center. Similarly, Arsenault et al., who prepared enzyme crosslinked aggregates based on LAC and CHI, observed that the kinetic parameters and catalytic efficiency of the obtained aggregates are strongly dependent on the amount of used CHI⁶⁴. Likewise, Li et al. reported that the interaction of β -galactosidase with CHI leads to higher reaction rates and better catalytic efficiency as a function of CHI concentration⁴¹. Recently, Ou et al. reported an important enhancement in the catalytic activity of catalase upon embedment in CHI/ hyaluronic acid ternary complexes, accompanied by an increase in K_m and the turnover number⁶⁵.

Table 4. Kinetic parameters of ABTS oxidation at pH = 4.5 by free and complexed LAC.

Sample	K_m (μM)	V_{max} ($\mu\text{M min}^{-1}$)	k_{cat} (min^{-1})
LAC	41.82 \pm 2.7	6.57 \pm 0.021	2.30 \pm 0.007
LAC/CHI _{0.5}	42.13 \pm 1.5	6.64 \pm 0.220	2.33 \pm 0.079
LAC/CHI ₂	65.23 \pm 2.6	7.91 \pm 0.001	2.77 \pm 0.006

K_m – Michaelis-Menten constant; V_{max} - maximum reaction rate, k_{cat} – turnover number

The catalytic activity of free or complexed LAC was also assessed in the enzymatic degradation of a model organic compound, that is, IC. The degradation test for IC was performed using SG as redox mediator, at different dye concentrations to evaluate its impact on the catalytic performance of the biocatalysts.

The degradation of IC was fully achieved using both LAC and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies at all the tested dye concentrations (**Figure S4, Supporting information**). As expected, the degradation rate, correlated with the increase in the time needed to achieve the full IC degradation (**Figure 9**),

decreased with the increase in dye concentrations, indicating potential mass transfer limitations resulting from the presence of excess dye molecules in the proximity of the enzyme binding sites or by the self-aggregation or agglomeration of the dye molecules.

Figure 9. Time needed for the full degradation of IC at different solution concentrations, in the presence of LAC/CHI₂, LAC/CHI_{0.5} and LAC.

In what concerns the role of CHI binding on the enzymatic degradation of IC, a rather curious trend can be observed (**Figure S4, Supplementary information**). For all tested dye concentrations, the degradation rate is almost constant for both free LAC and the LAC/CHI_r complexes in the first 20-30 minutes of contact, suggesting that during this initial phase, the interaction between the enzyme, mediator, and dye molecule occurs efficiently, and the catalytic sites are likely saturated. As the reaction proceeds, different enzymatic degradation profiles are observed for the free LAC and the LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies. The full degradation of the IC dye was obtained in a longer time in the case of LAC/CHI₂ complexes as compared to LAC/CHI_{0.5}, a behaviour that further confirms that the dye degradation is a diffusion-limited process, the presence of more CHI chains in the system hindering the accessibility to the active site of LAC. The

observed diffusional limitations might be ascribed to the presence of a thicker or more compact polymeric shell, which can act as a physical barrier, preventing the interaction between the catalytic site of the enzyme and the dye molecule. Such a behaviour is commonly reported in the case of immobilised or polymer-coated enzymes, as also described elsewhere^{4,66}. This effect is especially important in the context of IC degradation since the complex chemical structure of IC limits its accessibility to the enzyme catalytic center, while the presence of a conjugated system in the dye structure induces increased stability to enzymatic degradation. In this context, the choice of the biocatalyst used for the degradation of complex compounds such as dyes or other pollutants should take into consideration both diffusional limitations that might occur, but also the increase in stability of the enzyme upon the formation of polymer-based nanoassemblies. Nevertheless, the IC degradation is fully achieved using both LAC solution and LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies, demonstrating that such systems preserve the catalytic activity of LAC, even in the degradation of more complex substrates. While the dye degradation is slower for LAC/CHI nanoassemblies, their stability to environmental factors is higher, suggesting that they could outperform the LAC solution in the degradation of dyes in more complex environments.

CONCLUSION

The current paper provides a detailed study on the interaction of LAC, an oxidoreductase enzyme, with CHI, a naturally occurring polysaccharide. The study combined spectroscopic, computational and biochemical experiments to understand the binding behaviour and the impact of CHI complexation on the catalytic efficiency of LAC. Important insights into the binding of CHI to LAC were acquired from the fluorescence quenching experiments and the calculated binding constants from the Stern-Volmer model, which were further validated by the molecular

simulations performed, which confirmed the formation of CHI/LAC nanoassemblies. According to the performed experiments, the interaction of LAC with CHI occurs by a combination of electrostatic, hydrogen and van der Waals interactions, with the polysaccharide partially covering the surface of the enzyme. As evidenced from the DLS measurements, the size and stability of such nanoassemblies are dependent on the amount of used CHI, with larger nanoassemblies forming when larger amounts of CHI are used. Finally, the successful preservation of the catalytic activity of LAC embedded in such nanoassemblies was demonstrated by the enzymatic activity assays performed by ABTS oxidation and by the IC degradation tests, which highlighted improved stability of the nanoassemblies to pH and temperature variations as compared to the LAC solution. Collectively, the results sustain the idea that the interaction of LAC with CHI can lead to the formation of new protein/polymer nanoassemblies, characterised by increased stability in various conditions and with a suitable catalytic activity, that make them ideal candidates as catalysts for various processes.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Figure S1. Stern–Volmer (a) and double logarithmic Stern-Volmer (b) plots for the binding of CHI to LAC at the tested temperatures. **Figure S2.** Unaveraged RMSD evolution of LAC and LAC/CHI. **Figure S3.** Intensity-weighted size distributions of the LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies. **Figure S4.** Degradation of IC at 75 mg/L (a), 50 mg/L (b) and 25 mg/L (c), in the presence of LAC/CHI₂, LAC/CHI_{0.5} and LAC solution. **Table S1.** Number of contacts that appear between each amino acid in LAC structure and CHI. **Table S2.** Average diameter, polydispersity indexes and zeta potential values of the LAC/CHI_r nanoassemblies after 50 days of storage at 4 °C.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Marcela Mihai: marcela.mihai@icmpp.ro, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3193-0609>;

Stergios Pispas: pispas@eie.gr, <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5347-7430>

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Funding Sources

This work was financially supported by the Romanian Authority for Research, with project HYBSAC number PNRR-III-C9-2022-I8-201, within the National Recovery and Resilience Plan and by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, project BioMat4CAST, under grant agreement No 101086667.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors kindly acknowledged Dr. Daniela Rusu, Petru Poni Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry, for cooperation and STEM micrographs acquisition.

ABBREVIATIONS

ABTS 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid); CHI chitosan; DLS dynamic light scattering; IC Indigo Carmine; LAC Trametes versicolor laccase; MD molecular dynamics; PAA polyacrylic acid; PEO polyethylene oxide; PVS polyvinyl sulfonate; r mass ratio; RMSD Root-mean-square deviation; SG syringaldehyde; STEM scanning transmission electron microscopy.

REFERENCES

- (1) Arregui, L.; Ayala, M.; Gómez-Gil, X.; Gutiérrez-Soto, G.; Hernández-Luna, C.E.; Herrera De Los Santos, M.; Levin, L.; Rojo-Domínguez, A.; Romero-Martínez, D.; Saparrat, M.C.N.; Trujillo-Roldán, M.A.; Valdez-Cruz, N.A. Laccases: structure, function, and potential application in water bioremediation. *Microb. Cell Fact.* **2019**, *18*, 1–33.
- (2) Mot, A.C.; Silaghi-Dumitrescu, R. Laccases: Complex architectures for one-electron oxidations. *Biochemistry* **2012**, *77*, 1395-1407.
- (3) Rodríguez Couto, S. Dye removal by immobilised fungi. *Biotechnol Adv* **2009**, *27*, 227–235.
- (4) Bilal, M.; Rasheed, T.; Nabeel, F.; Iqbal, H.M.N.; Zhao, Y. Hazardous contaminants in the environment and their laccase-assisted degradation – A review. *J. Environ. Manage.* **2019**, *234*, 253-264.
- (5) Cano-Raya, C.; Dencheva, N.V.; Braz, J.F.; Malfois, M.; Denchev, Z.Z. Optical biosensor for catechol determination based on laccase-immobilized anionic polyamide 6 microparticles. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2020**, *137*, 49131.
- (6) Perna, V.; Meyer, A.S.; Holck, J.; Eltis, L.D.; Eijssink, V.G.H.; Wittrup Agger, J. Laccase-catalyzed oxidation of lignin induces production of H₂O₂. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *8*, 831-84.
- (7) Guo, S.; Li, H.; Liu, J.; Yang, Y.; Kong, W.; Qiao, S.; Huang, H.; Liu, Y.; Kang, Z. Visible-light-induced effects of au nanoparticle on laccase catalytic activity. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2015**, *7*, 20937–20944.
- (8) Lin, X.; Liu, H.; Tang, L.; Shi, M.; Xu, M.; Huang, Y.; Yi, Z.; Chen, H. Interaction between laccase and diethylstilbestrol based on multispectral and chromatography analyses. *J. Molec. Recognit.* **2022**, *35*, e2951.

- (9) Zhang, X.; Hua, M.; Lv, L.; Pan, B. Ionic polymer-coated laccase with high activity and enhanced stability: application in the decolourisation of water containing AO7. *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 8253.
- (10) Chaniotakis, N.A. Enzyme stabilization strategies based on electrolytes and polyelectrolytes for biosensor applications. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **2004**, *378*, 89–95.
- (11) Cooper, C.L.; Dubin, P.L.; Kayitmazer, A.B.; Turksen, S. Polyelectrolyte-protein complexes. *Curr. Opin. Colloid In* **2005**, *10*, 52-78.
- (12) Kim, S.; Sureka, H.V.; Kayitmazer, A.B.; Wang, G.; Swan, J.W.; Olsen, B.D. Effect of protein surface charge distribution on protein-polyelectrolyte complexation. *Biomacromolecules* **2020**, *21*, 3026–3037.
- (13) Kudaibergenov, S. E.; Jaeger, W.; Khutoryanskiy, V. V. Physicochemical aspects of polyelectrolyte complexes. *Adv Polym Sci* **2006**, *201*, 157-224.
- (14) Zhou, J.; Wan, Y.; Cohen Stuart, M.A.; Wang, M.; Wang, J. Effects of control factors on protein-polyelectrolyte complex coacervation. *Biomacromolecules*, **2023**, *24*, 5759–5768.
- (15) Gao, S.; Holkar, A.; Srivastava, S. Protein–polyelectrolyte complexes and micellar assemblies. *Polymers* **2019**, *11*, 1097.
- (16) Turgeon, S.L.; Schmitt, C.; Sanchez, C. Protein-polysaccharide complexes and coacervates. *Curr. Opin. Colloid In* **2007**, *12*, 166-178.
- (17) Cheung, R.C.F.; Ng, T.B.; Wong, J.H.; Chan, W.Y. Chitosan: an update on potential biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. *Marine Drugs* **2015**, *13*, 5156–5186.
- (18) Yu, Y.; Su, Z.; Peng, Y.; Zhong, Y.; Wang, L.; Xin, M.; Li, M. Recent advances in modifications, biotechnology, and biomedical applications of chitosan-based materials: A review. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2024**, *289*, 138772.

- (19) Kou, S.; Peters, L.; Mucalo, M. Chitosan: A review of molecular structure, bioactivities and interactions with the human body and micro-organisms. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2022**, *282*, 119132.
- (20) Tran, C.D.; Mututuvvari, T.M. Cellulose, Chitosan, and keratin composite materials. Controlled drug release. *Langmuir* **2015**, *31*, 1516–1526.
- (21) Regiel-Futyra, A.; Kus-Liškiewicz, M.; Sebastian, V.; Irusta, S.; Arruebo, M.; Stochel, G.; Kyziół, A. Development of noncytotoxic chitosan–gold nanocomposites as efficient antibacterial materials. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2015**, *7*, 1087–1099.
- (22) Briones, A.V.; Sato, T. Encapsulation of glucose oxidase (GOD) in polyelectrolyte complexes of chitosan-carrageenan. *React. Funct. Polym.* **2010**, *70*, 19–27.
- (23) Gao, Y.; Wu, Y. Recent advances of chitosan-based nanoparticles for biomedical and biotechnological applications. *Int. J. Biol. Macrom.* **2022**, *203*, 379–388.
- (24) Wu, D.; Zhu, L.; Li, Y.; Zhang, X.; Xu, S.; Yang, G.; Delair, T. Chitosan-based colloidal polyelectrolyte complexes for drug delivery: a review. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2020**, *238*, 116126
- (25) Teotia, A.; Laurén, I.; Borandeh, S.; Seppälä, J. Quaternized chitosan derivatives as viable antiviral agents: structure–activity correlations and mechanisms of action. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2023**, *15*, 18707–18719.
- (26) Rinaudo, M. Chitin and chitosan: Properties and applications. *Prog Polym Sci* **2006**, *31*, 603-632.
- (27) Yu, Y., Su, Z., Peng, Y., Zhing, Y., Wang, L., Xin, M., Li, M. Recent advances in modifications, biotechnology, and biomedical applications of chitosan-based materials: A review. *Int. J. Biol. Macrom.* **2025**, *289*, 138772.
- (28) Bekale, L.; Agudelo, D.; Tajmir-Riahi, H.A. Effect of polymer molecular weight on chitosan–protein interaction. *Col. Surf. B* **2015**, *125*, 309–317.

- (29) Veselova, I.A.; Kireiko, A.V.; Shekhovtsova, T.N. Catalytic activity and the stability of horseradish peroxidase increase as a result of its incorporation into a polyelectrolyte complex with chitosan. *Appl. Biochem. Microbiol.* **2009**, *45*, 125–129.
- (30) Boeris, V.; Romanini, D.; Farruggia, B.; Picó, G. Interaction and complex formation between catalase and cationic polyelectrolytes: Chitosan and Eudragit E100. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2009**, *45*, 103–108.
- (31) Boeris, V.; Micheletto, Y.; Lionzo, M.; da Silveira, N. P.; Picó, G. Interaction behavior between chitosan and pepsin. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2011**, *84*, 459–464.
- (32) Petrila, L. M.; Bucatariu, F.; Stoica, I.; Mihai, M.; & Froidevaux, R. A green approach combining polyelectrolyte-based core-shell microparticles and laccase for Indigo Carmine degradation. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* **2025**, *13*, 115631.
- (33) Bertrand, T.; Jolival, C.; Briozzo, P.; Caminade, E.; Joly, N.; Madzak, C.; Mougín, C. Crystal structure of a four-copper laccase complexed with an arylamine: Insights into substrate recognition and correlation with kinetics. *Biochemistry* **2002**, *41*, 7325–7333.
- (34) Abraham, M.J.; Murtola, T.; Schulz, R.; Páll, S.; Smith, J.C.; Hess, B.; Lindahl, E. GROMACS: High performance molecular simulations through multi-level parallelism from laptops to supercomputers. *SoftwareX* **2015**, *1–2*, 19–25.
- (35) Zhang X. F.; Yang G.Y.; Zhang Y.; Xie Y.; Withers S.G.; Feng Y. A general and efficient strategy for generating the stable enzymes. *Sci Rep.* **2016**, *26*; 6:33797
- (36) Saoudi, O.; Ghaouar, N.; Othman, T. Fluorescence study of laccase from *Trametes versicolor* under the effects of pH, chemical denaturants and ionic liquids. *J. Mol. Liq.* **2017**, *225*, 56–63.

(37) dos Santos Rodrigues, F.H.; Delgado, G.G.; Santana da Costa, T.; Tasic, L. Applications of fluorescence spectroscopy in protein conformational changes and intermolecular contacts. *BBA Advances* **2023**, *3*, 100091.

(38) Wang, H.; Wang, N.; Chen, X.; Wu, Z.; Zhong, W.; Yu, D.; Zhang, H. Effects of moderate electric field on the structural properties and aggregation characteristics of soybean protein isolate. *Food Hydrocoll.* **2022**, *133*, 107911.

(39) Lakowicz, J.R. (2006). Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy. 3rd Edition, Springer, Berlin.

(40) Tong, W.; Liu, X. Y.; Yang, Y.; Wang, Y.; Huang, Z.; Fan, H. Molecular and technical aspects on the interaction of bovine serum albumin with pyrazine derivatives: From molecular docking to spectroscopy study. *J. Food Sci.* **2025**, *90*, e70017.

(41) Li, Z.; Wang, H.; Chen, S.; Li, J.; Zheng, C.; Liu, Y.; Hao, C. Molecular studies between chitosan and graphene oxide-chitosan nanocomposites with β -galactosidase: From interaction mechanism to structural and functional changes. *J. Mol. Struct.* **2025**, *1325*, 140992.

(42) Antonov, Y.A.; Kulikov, S.N.; Bezrodnykh, E.A.; Zhuravleva, I.L.; Berezin, B.B.; Tikhonov, V.E. An insight into the effect of interaction with protein on antibacterial activity of chitosan derivatives. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2024**, *259*, 129050.

(43) Ma, N.; Wang, L.; Zhou, L.; Wan, Y.; Ding, S.; Qian, W. Analysis of the interaction between chitosan with different molecular weights and casein based on optical interferometry. *Food Hydrocoll.* **2023**, *137*, 108386.

(44) Leite Milião, G.; de Souza Soares, L.; Balbino, D.F.; de Almeida Alves Barbosa, É.; Bressan, G C.; de Carvalho Teixeira, A.V.N.; dos Reis Coimbra, J.S.; de Oliveira, E.B. pH

influence on the mechanisms of interaction between chitosan and ovalbumin: a multi-spectroscopic approach. *Food Hydrocoll.* **2022**, *123*, 107137.

(45) Agudelo, D.; Nafisi, S.; Tajmir-Riahi, H.A. Encapsulation of milk β -lactoglobulin by chitosan nanoparticles. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2013**, *117*, 6403–6409.

(46) Liu, X.; Xia, W.; Jiang, Q.; Xu, Y.; Yu, P. Binding of a novel bacteriostatic agent—chitosan oligosaccharides–kojic acid graft copolymer to bovine serum albumin: spectroscopic and conformation investigations. *Eur. Food Res. Technol.* **2015**, *240*, 109–118.

(47) Asemi-Esfahani, Z.; Shareghi, B.; Farhadian, S.; Momeni, L. Food additive dye–lysozyme complexation: Determination of binding constants and binding sites by fluorescence spectroscopy and modeling methods. *J. Mol. Liq.* **2022**, *363*, 119749.

(48) Dehdasht-Heidari, N.; Shareghi, B.; Farhadian, S.; Momeni, L. Investigation on the interaction behavior between safranal and pepsin by spectral and MD simulation studies. *J. Mol. Liq.* **2021**, *344*, 117903.

(49) Habibian Dehkordi, S.; Farhadian, S.; Ghasemi, M. The interaction between the azo dye tartrazine and α -Chymotrypsin enzyme: Molecular dynamics simulation and multi-spectroscopic investigations. *J. Mol. Liq.* **2021**, *344*, 117931.

(50) Gholizadeh, M.; Shareghi, B.; Farhadian, S.; Farokhvand, N. Thermodynamic investigation of dicyclohexyl phthalate complex formation with α -Chymotrypsin using in silico and analytical methods. *J. Mol. Liq.* **2024**, *410*, 125572.

(51) Ross, P. D.; Subramanian, S. Thermodynamics of Protein Association Reactions: Forces Contributing to Stability. *Biochemistry* **1981**, *20*, 3096–3102.

(52) Sun, Y.; Wei, S.; Yin, C.; Liu, L.; Hu, C.; Zhao, Y.; Ye, Y.; Hu, X.; Fan, J. Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of 4-butoxyethoxy-N-octadecyl-1,8-naphthalimide as a new

fluorescent probe for the determination of proteins. *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* **2011**, *21*, 3798–3804.

(53) Lončar, N.; Božić, N.; Vujčić, Z. Expression and characterization of a thermostable organic solvent-tolerant laccase from *Bacillus licheniformis* ATCC 9945a. *J. Mol. Catal. B Enzym.* **2016**, *134*, 390-395.

(54) Karayianni, M.; Lotos, E.D.; Mihai, M.; Pispas, S. Coassembly of a hybrid synthetic–biological chitosan-g-poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) copolymer with DNAs of different lengths. *Polymers* **2024**, *16*, 3101.

(55) Li, Q.; Zhao, Z. Characterization of the structural and colloidal properties of α -lactalbumin/chitosan complexes as a function of heating. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2018**, *66*, 972–978.

(56) Bourouis, I.; McClements, D. J.; Li, H.; Pang, Z.; Liu, X. Interaction mechanism between soy protein microgels and chitosan and the resulting physical properties: effect of biopolymer ratio, pH and ionic strength. *Food Hydrocoll.* **2025**, *168*, 111557.

(57) Sun, Y.; Zhao, Y.; Qiu, M.; Zhang, Y.; Liang, J.; Xie, S.; Li, R.; Wang, X. Preparation, characterization, stability and application of the H-type aggregates lutein/whey protein/chitosan nanoparticles. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2024**, *282*, 136739.

(58) Zhang, H.; Yu, H.; Mei, J.; Zhang, Y.; & Deng, Z. Preparation, characterization and in vitro release of β -galactosidase loaded polyelectrolyte nanoparticles. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2018**, *115*, 1–9.

(59) Gärdlund, L.; Wågberg, L.; Norgren, M. New insights into the structure of polyelectrolyte complexes. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2007**, *312*, 237–246.

(60) Zaharia, M.M.; Bucatariu, F.; Karayianni, M.; Lotos, E.D.; Mihai, M.; Pispas, S. Synthesis of thermoresponsive chitosan-graft-poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) hybrid copolymer and its complexation with DNA, *Polymers* **2024**, *16*, 1315.

(61) Boeris, V.; Farruggia, B.; Nerli, B.; Romanini, D.; Picó, G. Protein-flexible chain polymer interactions to explain protein partition in aqueous two-phase systems and the protein–polyelectrolyte complex formation. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2007**, *41*, 286–294.

(62) Melo, M.N.; Pereira, F.M.; Rocha, M.A.; Ribeiro, J.G.; Diz, F.M.; Monteiro, W.F.; Ligabue, R. A.; Severino, P.; Fricks, A.T. Immobilization and characterization of horseradish peroxidase into chitosan and chitosan/PEG nanoparticles: A comparative study. *Process Biochem.* **2020**, *98*, 160–171.

(63) Wang, X.; Bowman, J.; Tu, S.; Nykypanchuk, D.; Kuksenok, O.; Minko, S. Polyethylene glycol crowder's effect on enzyme aggregation, thermal stability, and residual catalytic activity. *Langmuir* **2021**, *37*, 8474–8485.

(64) Arsenault, A.; Cabana, H.; Jones, J.P. Laccase-based CLEAs: chitosan as a novel cross-linking agent. *Enzyme Res.* **2011**, *1*, 376015.

(65) Ou, X.; Tang, Z.; Ye, Y.; Chen, X.; Huang, Y. Macromolecular crowding effect on chitosan-hyaluronic acid complexation and the activity of encapsulated catalase. *Biomacromolecules* **2024**, *25*, 3840–3849.

(66) Zhou, W.; Zhang, W.; Cai, Y. Laccase immobilization for water purification: A comprehensive review. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2021**, *403*, 126272.

BRIEFS

Nanoassemblies between *Trametes versicolor* laccase and chitosan, investigated through fluorescence quenching and molecular dynamic simulations, show application as catalysts under various conditions, verified with ABTS for relative activity determination and Indigo Carmin for dye degradation.

SYNOPSIS

Relative catalytic activity (%)

Time needed for IC degradation (min)

